

LINGUISTIC RESEARCH OF TEXT, INTERTEXT AND HYPERTEXT: A MOLDAVIAN EXPERIENCE

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Abstract

The following paper is a review of the book by E. Ungureanu "Dincolo de text: HYPERTEXTUL"¹, which contains a profound linguistic analysis of a conceptual triad: text – intertext – hypertext. In this hardback edition the author gives rise to theoretical discussion of the afore-mentioned concepts and suggests making them the main ones in the general theory of text. E.Ungureanu thinks that it will help open new areas of linguistic study which could be termed as "intertextology" and "hypertextology".

Keywords: computer-mediated communication, electronic hypertext, hyperlink, hypertext, hypertextuality, intertext, intertextuality, research, review, text, text-term-list.

Over the last decades scientists all over the world have frequently claimed that traditional communication has completely changed and become more computer-mediated due to the existence of the Internet and the World Wide Web (D. Crystal², O. Dedova³, L. Schipitsina⁴). E-mails, blogs, chats, social networks, instant messaging, comments of Internet users, etc. have changed a traditional linear text into a more interactive, dynamic, unstable and visual one. While traditional linear texts in general form a single reading sequence, texts in a hypertext environment split up, recombine and provide simultaneously existing reading paths. Even if the reader re-linearises the hypertext while reading it, the text itself structurally remains a network. Non-linear electronic text (e-text) with hyperlinks or hypertext demands creation of new scientific methods and tools which are considered to be in their initial phase of study. That is why scientists become more interested in linguistic research of computer-mediated communication, hypertext and electronic hypertext.

An example of considerable linguistic study of a conceptual triad: *text – intertext – hypertext* can be found in the book by Moldavian Doctor of Philology E. Ungureanu "Dincolo de text: HYPERTEXTUL":

In this hardback edition the author gives rise to theoretical discussion of the afore-mentioned concepts and suggests making them the main ones in the general theory of text. E. Ungureanu thinks that it will help open new areas of linguistic study which could be termed as “intertextology” and “hypertextology”. The reviewed book is supposed to be the result of laborious and convincing research that has been conducted with the use of traditional concepts of humanities as well as new concepts of computer science.

The book “Dincolo de text: Hypertextul” (“Beyond the Text: Hypertext”) by E. Ungureanu consists of three main chapters: 1. Text (pp. 13–50); 2. Intertext (pp. 51–97); 3. Hypertext (pp. 98–243); at the end of the book there is a Post-text: New Tower of Babel (pp. 244–248) and a very extensive Bibliography/Webography (pp. 249–280). Chapter 2 and Chapter 3 also contain Case Studies (pp. 76–97, pp. 212–243).

The first chapter “Text” examines the nature of text as a sign and language (1.1.), poetic text as absolute language (1.2.) and defines a great variety of text-terms (1.3.). In this part of the book the author follows R.Barthes, who drew an analogy between text and textiles, declaring that “a text is a tissue [or fabric] of quotations, drawn from innumerable centers of culture, rather than from one, individual experience”⁵. In Barthes’s words, every text holds the intertextual, itself being the text-between of another text, quite different to its sources, but nevertheless, marking the influences, falling in with the myth of filiation, even whilst of and in citations that are anonymous, untraceable and yet already read: they are quotations without inverted commas⁶. New ways of reading and writing texts online allow E.Ungureanu to adapt Barthes’s words and declare that a hypertext is a tissue [or fabric] and every hypertext holds the intertextual online on the Internet.

The author offers a highly creative approach of making a glossary of more than 65 text-terms in the third part of the first chapter “Textul și -textele” (1.3.). The glossary includes: Alotext, Antetext, Antitext, Arhetext,

Arhitext, Autotext, Avantext, Blogtext, Chat-Text, Context, Contratext, Copytext, Cotext, Cronotext, Cybertext, Cvasitext, Digitext, Epitext, Exotext, E-text, Extratext, Fenotext, Genotext, Hipertext, Hipotext, Hypertext, Iconotext, Infratext, Intertext, Intext, Intratext, Macrotext, Maxitext, Megatext, Metatext, Microtext, Miditext, Minitext, Nanotext, Nontext, Ontotext, Palim(p)text, Paratext, Peritext, Post-text, Pretext, Prototext, Pseudotext, Semiotext, SMS-text, Spacetext, Stereotext, Stretchtext, Subtext, Supratext, Teletext, Text, Totext, Transtext, Unitext, Videotext, Webtext, Wikitext, Wordtext, Xenotext, etc. This part of the book is supposed to open prospects for further study as it has an online version on the website of Information Society Development Institute (<http://idsi.md/textul-si-textele>). The list remains open, the author suggests, quoting E. Coseriu: "Language is always open for future opportunities". Online access and downloading of the text-term-list will be controlled by Instrument Bibliometric National (<http://www.ibn.idsi.md>) that will help increase the visibility of scientific projects results financed by the state and the number of knowledge consumers.

The second chapter "Intertext" offers in depth discussions of intertext and intertextuality, based on scientific papers by J. Derrida, U. Eco, N. Fateeva, E. Goroshko, J. Kristeva, who is believed to be the inventor of the term intertextuality, and others. In this part of the book the author aims to define text as an intertext (2.1.), attempts to explain the difference between repeated discourse (E. Coseriu) and free discourse, claiming that hypertext is based on the theory of repetition (2.2.), and comments on quotations, references and plagiarism which are considered to be the main concepts of intertext (2.3.).

The third chapter "Hypertext" is the main part of the book, where the author defines hypertext as a hypermedia text with a lot of hyperlinks (p. 110). In this part the author aims to define a digital text (3.1.), deals with the metaphor of the Internet (3.1.1.), examines the nature of electronic hypertext and provides a short history of hypertext (V. Bush, D. Engelbart, T. Nelson) (3.1.2.), examines the characteristics of hypertext (3.1.3.): nonlinearity, dynamism, creativity, virtuality, globality, fragmentariness, decentralization, instability, visibility, interactivity, polyphony, openness, equality, infinity, heterogeneity, multimediality (hypermediality), anonymity, depersonalization, identity, duplicity, temporary and spatial independence, integrability, kreolization, etc. Part 3.2. is devoted to Internet linguistics, where the author attempts to show that hypertext is the main concept of Internet linguistics (3.2.1.). The structure of hypertext is analysed in part 3.2.2., where the author studies the main elements of hypertext: a texton (3.2.2.1.) and a hyperlink as the main means of cohesion and coherence in hypertext (3.2.2.2.).

The author of the book states in the third chapter that hypertext, considered the third dimension of the language (M. Bernard), uses hyperlink, which is its engine, as the fundamental concept. Without hyperlinks in the text area of Internet the users of electronic texts would be as if with no routes or traffic signs. Following G. Genette theories, E. Ungureanu claims that hyperlink can be considered modern hyperparatext, which generates hypermeaning. This is due to the hyperlink dynamism as a default feature of the linguistic technological sign and its omniscience (the possibility to be positioned anywhere in the peritext, i.e. intra- and extratext) and its interactivity, which is the direct connection with the user (through epitext).

Finally and most importantly, E. Ungureanu thoroughly analyses in the last part of the third chapter "Hypertextul și hypertextele" (3.3.) quotations (3.3.1.), references (3.3.2.), the Bible and the library (3.3.3.), Wikipedia (3.3.4.) and hypertext literature (3.3.5.) as examples of hypertext practices that ideally reflect the history of humanity as hypertext.

The results of E. Ungureanu's study were also evaluated and assessed in the second "Hypertext as the subject of linguistic research" conference proceedings: UNGUREANU, E. *The Bible, the library and "Biblio"-net as hypertext* // Hypertext as the subject of linguistic research: the second international conference proceedings. Samara: SSASSH, 2011 (<http://www.стройков.рф/hypertext2.html>) and the third "Hypertext as the subject of linguistic research" conference proceedings: UNGUREANU, E. COJOCARU, Ig., COJOCARU, Ir. *Hyperlink as hypersign and paratext* // Hypertext as the subject of linguistic research: the third international conference proceedings. Samara: SSASSH, 2013 (<http://www.стройков.рф/hypertext3.html>).

In conclusion we can say that the book is clearly written and well researched. Whether or not one agrees with the author's arguments, the book is stimulating, informative and thought-provoking. We hope that this book will significantly contribute to linguistic research of hypertext, and we believe that her book urgently needs to be translated into the English language.

We would like to thank Moldavian Doctor of Philology E. Ungureanu for giving us an opportunity to look through her book containing such a considerable linguistic study of a conceptual triad: *text – intertext – hypertext*. We wish the author success and new creative fulfillments, and we are looking forward to continuing our collaboration.

Notes

¹Ungureanu, 2014.

²Crystal, 2004.

³Dedova, 2008.

⁴Schipitsina, 2010.

⁵Ungureanu, 2014, p. 15.

⁶Ungureanu, 2014, p. 17.

References

CRYSTAL, D. *Language and the Internet*. Cambridge: CUP, 2004 [=Crystal, 2004].

DEDOVA, O. *Theory of Hypertext and Hypertext Practices in the Runet*. Moscow: MAKS Press, 2008 [=Dedova, 2008].

SCHIPITSINA, L. *Computer-Mediated Communication: Linguistic Aspect of Analysis*. Moscow: KRASAND, 2010 [=Schipitsina, 2010].

UNGUREANU, E. *Dincolo de text: hypertextul*. Chişinău: Arc, 2014 [=Ungureanu, 2014].